

Syntactic Nominalization In Balinese: A Study of Noun Formation Through The 'Ane' Marker

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Abstract

Nominalization;
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This study aims to investigate the syntactic formation of nouns in Balinese, a language spoken in Indonesia. The research draws on a diverse range of primary data sources, including written texts from storybooks (Satua Bali), Balinese short stories (Pupulan), the Bali Orti newspaper, and online dictionaries, as well as oral data collected from native Balinese speakers and the author's own intuition as a fluent speaker of the language. The data collection process involved a thorough examination of the selected texts, followed by the identification of nouns and their corresponding markers, specifically the 'ane' marker. The analysis employed the distributional method, utilizing techniques such as mark reading and direct element division (Sudaryanto, 1988; Zaim, 2014: 101-102). The theoretical framework adopted in this study is rooted in Morphological Theory, as outlined by Katamba and Stonham (2006), which focuses on grammatical relations. The research findings indicate that the process of reducing nouns in Balinese can be achieved through a syntactic strategy, specifically by employing the 'ane' marker. Furthermore, the constituents derived through this marker originate from both transitive and intransitive sentences. This study contributes to a deeper understanding of the syntactic formation of nouns in Balinese and sheds light on the language's unique grammatical structures.

1. Introduction

Research on the Balinese language system has been conducted by both local and foreign linguists. However, there is still very little research on Balinese nominalization. Nominalization research is to be researched. Nominalization is an important concept in linguistic studies because nominalization is the process of turning words into nouns. Halliday, (2004:358) states that nominalization refers to

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the phenomenon that any element or group of elements, phrases, or clauses can function as a nominal structure. In line with that, Shibatani, (2019:21) also states that nominalization is a metonymic-based grammatical derivation process that produces constructions related to denotation consisting of concept entities metonymically evoked by nominalization structures, such as events, facts, propositions, and products produced and event participants. The two statements above can be concluded that nominalization includes not only lexical words but also clauses, nominalization is not always a real referent but also a concept, as well as constituents that behave like nouns. The verb as the center of the clause needs an argument with a noun class. Based on this, this study is very important, because the nominalization process of each language has morphological and syntactic language characteristics, so the results of the study will be theoretical input cross-linguistically. The study of nominalization morphologically through affixation, reduplication, and fusion has been discussed a lot. However, syntactic nominalization studies are still rare. In Balinese, syntactical nominalization studies use several markers. One of them is the 'ane' marker.

There are studies on nominalization with the Balinese 'ane' marker that have discussed it. Although it is still very rare to find. Saryana (2017) and Trisnawati (2015) in their articles examine the process of noun formation (nominalization) and noun structure in Balinese. The results of their research state that the formation of derived nouns can be done through the combination of lexical elements into phrases, and the reduction of clauses into noun phrases. There are two kinds of derived nouns formed by reducing clauses into noun phrases, namely nouns derived through relativization with ane/sane. However, the 'ane' discussed is a noun in the form of a noun phrase that has a head which is a noun phrase with a nucleus.

The two studies above provide information on the formation of nouns derived from clauses. However, headless nominalization is not discussed. Therefore, this study examines nominalization derived from clauses using the marker 'ane' which does not have a head. This study was chosen because the process of nominalization in each language has morphological and syntactic characteristics. More specifically, this study aims to find out the morphological and syntactic language characteristics, so that the results of the study can be theoretical input cross-linguistically. The results of this study are expected to be able to provide new references on nominalization as a development of previous Balinese language studies and can provide input to linguists who pursue linguistics related to cross-language nominalization. In this research, the Morphological Theory according to Katamba and Stonham (2006) regarding grammatical relations is used. In grammatical relations, it is necessary to clarify the difference between syntactic categories, grammatical relations (also called grammatical functions or syntactic functions), or theta roles. Syntactic categories such as noun phrases and verb phrases determine the syntactic type of a particular constituent. The syntactic type of a constituent is determined by the category of the constituent's head. A noun phrase is a constituent whose head is a noun, while a verb phrase is a constituent whose head is a verb, and so on. A theta role (e.g., agent, patient, or instrument), mentions the semantic relationship between a predicate and its argument. It is determined not by semantic considerations, but by the syntactic position of the particular constituent. The grammatical relations used are verb, phrase, subject, object, second object, and oblique.

2. Material and Method

2.1 Materials

This study employs a qualitative research approach, wherein the primary data consists of linguistic data in the form of words, clauses, and sentences. The majority of the data is comprised of Balinese language samples, which were carefully collected from a range of primary sources, both written and

oral. The written data corpus was compiled from a variety of sources, including traditional Balinese storybooks (Satua Bali), Balinese short stories, and articles from the Bali Orti newspaper. Additionally, the researcher consulted online dictionaries specializing in the Balinese language to gather further written data. In terms of oral data, the researcher conducted interviews with native Balinese speakers, who provided valuable insights into the language's grammatical structures and nuances. Furthermore, as a native Balinese speaker themselves, the researcher drew upon their own linguistic intuition to inform the data collection process. This multi-faceted approach enabled the researcher to gather a rich and diverse dataset, which was subsequently analyzed to identify patterns and trends in the nominalization process in Balinese.

2.2 Methods

The data collection process involves a thorough examination of the predetermined data source through a combination of reading and listening. Within the data source, nouns are identified in the texts. The researcher employs specific markers to distinguish certain words or forms as nouns. Subsequently, the nouns are carefully re-examined and re-listened to repeatedly. Nouns marked by the 'ane' suffix are then identified. Following this, the data is analyzed using the distributional method, which incorporates two techniques: the mark reading technique and the direct element dividing technique (Sudaryanto, 1988; Zaim, 2014: 101-102).

3. Results and Discussion

The subject in Balinese sentence construction can be filled by constituents containing verbs. The position of the verb in the subject function can be referred to as a noun because the verb undergoes a transposition process, namely from its position as a predicate and then switching functions as a subject. However, in Balinese there is no stand-alone verb in its function as subject, but it is marked by the lexicon 'ane'. The conjunction *ane* functions as a pronoun that connects clauses in a sentence and refers to someone or something mentioned earlier. The function of *ane* as a pronoun that refers to someone or something is a function that shows that 'ane' can form a constituent undergoing a nominalization process into a noun or noun phrase. The following are examples of clauses containing subjects with the *ane* marker.

1. *Ane lakar simpen Bapak ento (Subj) lung warnane (Pred).*
 'The one that I (father) will keep is good in color' (author's intuition:2023)

Sentence 1 is a clause construction data that has its subject derived from verbs. Because of its subject position, the noun phrase can be said to be a noun category. However, this is not the only reason for calling the constituent of the phrase a noun phrase, but also because of the *ane* 'yang' and *ento* 'that' markers. *Ento* 'that' can function as a connector or marker that the verb construction is nominalized, the constituent that occupies the subject is a noun. Sentence 1, if *ento* is not added, the clause construction changes to *Ane lakar simpen Bapak lung gati warnanya* 'Which Bapak will keep the color of'.

2. *Ane lakar simpen Bapak (Subj) lung warnane (Pred).*
 'The one that I (father) will keep is good in color.' (author's intuition:2023)

The construction of clause 2 is grammatical so it can be seen that the nominalization process can be marked by the combination of *ane* 'that' and *ento* 'that', but *ane* 'that' can also stand alone. Constructions 1 and 2 are derived from the following sentences.

3. Bapak (Subj) laku nyimpen (Pred) baju ento (Obj).
'I (Father) will keep your clothes.' (author's intuition:2023)

Sentence 3 is a transitive sentence construction, which is a sentence that has both subject and object nominations. The following example is an example of a sentence derived from an intransitive sentence.

4. Ia melaib.
'He runs.' (author's intuition:2023)

The sentence can be nominalized into a noun phrase as in the following example.

5. Ane melaib ento (Subj) kurenan tiange (Pred).
'The one running was my wife.' (author's intuition:2024)

Based on the data above, it is known that bitransitive and ekatransitive sentences can be nominalized with the lexicon *ane* 'that' combined with the demonstrative *ento* 'that'.

6. Ane besik ene (Subj) laku simpen (Pred) Bapak.
'This one I (father) will keep.' (Bali Orti: 2019)

In the data above, clause 6 consists of the constituent *ane besik ene* which is categorized as a noun because in the clause it occupies the syntactic function as subject. Then, *laku simpen* 'will be stored' is a verb that functions as a predicate. *Ene* 'this' in the constituent is a demonstrative clue word that refers to a certain object. The actor in the sentence above is Mr. with the noun class. Sentence 6 is derived from the transitive sentence *Bapak laku nyimpen ane besik ne* 'Bapak will keep this one.' This sentence is transitive. Then, the object function is filled by the constituent *ane besik ne* moving forward to become the subject in the sentence.

7. Ane pelihange (Subj) tuah anak luh ane kasungguh bekung (Pred).
'The blame is on women who are called barren.' (Bali Orti:2019)

Clause 7 above consists of the constituents *ane pelihanga* 'the one blamed' which functions as the subject and *anak luh ane kasungguh bekung* 'the woman called barren' which functions as the predicate. The constituent *ane pelihanga* is a noun-categorized constituent. This is because of its position as the subject and is marked by *ane* and constituents that occupy the function of the subject are always nouns. In the sentence above, the subject of the action of *pelihanga* is *anak luh ane kasungguh bekung*. The core of the constituent *ane pelihanga* is the verb *pelihanga* 'to blame' which is a passive verb. Therefore, we can trace that the sentence above comes from the intransitive sentence *anak luh ane kasungguh bekung pelih* 'the woman called barren is wrong' which is filled by the verb *pelih* 'wrong'. In the intransitive sentence, the constituent *anak luh ane kasungguh bekung* is the subject and the verb *pelih* is the predicate.

8. Ane kadute di basangne (Subj) tusing panak tiange sujati (Pred)
sakewala tiang tusing nyangetang.
'The one in her belly was not my real child, but I didn't care.'

(Bali Orti: 2018)

Clause 8 above consists of a noun constituent in the form of the noun phrase *ane kadute di basangne* 'the one carried in the stomach' functioning as the subject. The constituent *tusing panak tiange sujati* 'not my real child' functions as the predicate. The sentence above is derived from the transitive sentence *kurenan tiange ngadut panak ane tusing panak tiange sujati* 'my wife carries (in the stomach) a child who is not really my child' in the clause. The sentence consists of the constituent *kurenan tiange* 'my wife' which occupies the function of subject with the class of possessive noun phrase. The predicate is implied by the verb *ngadut* 'to carry (by placing between the cloth or *kamben* and the waist, but in this case in the stomach)' functioning as a predicate. The constituent *panak ane panak tiange sujati* 'a child who is not my child' is a possessive noun phrase. The verb *ngadut* pada becomes passive.

9. *Ane ngangganen* (Subj) *tusing ade* (Pred).
'There are no representatives.' (Bali Orti: 2018)

Clause 9 above consists of the constituents *ane ngangganen* 'who represents' and *tusing ade* 'no one'. Each is a noun and verb class. In the sentence structure, they occupy syntactic functions as subject and predicate. The constituent *ane ngangganen* is a noun class constituent because it occupies the function of subject in the sentence. The sentence above is derived from the sentence *tusing ade ane ngangganen* 'no one represents.' The verb *ngangganen* in this original sentence does not change form. The constituent *ane ngangganen* is a transitive verb which in this case the verb does not change, it remains a transitive verb.

10. *Ane cenikan makaput ulatan ental putih* (Subj) *aji slae tali Bu..*'
'The smaller one wrapped in white palmyra is 25,000 Mam..' (Bali Orti: 2019)

In sentence 10 above, the constituent *ane cenikan makaput ulatan ental putih* 'the smaller one is wrapped in woven white palm leaves' is the constituent that functions as the subject in the sentence above. The subject and object in the sentence are filled with nouns. Based on this, the constituent *ane cenikan makaput ulatan ental putih* can be said to be a noun category. The 'ane' mark at the beginning of the constituent is a noun marker. The sentence above is a sentence derived or derived from the constituent ...(object) *cenikan makaput ulatan ental putih*.

11. *Ane buin besikan* (Subj), *tusing nawang pasubayan miwah pitutur utama* (Pred).
'The other one, doesn't know the main agreement and advice.' (I Tuma Teken I Titih:37)

In sentence 11 above, the constituent *ane buin besikan* 'the other one' is a constituent that functions as the subject in the sentence above. Because it occupies the function of the subject, the constituent *ane buin besikan* is a constituent with the category of noun. The 'ane' mark at the beginning of the constituent is a noun marker. The constituent above is derived from the sentence *that ada (someone) tusing nawang pasubayan miwah pitutur utama* 'someone does not know the promise and the main advice.'

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings of this study demonstrate that the process of nominalization in Balinese can be achieved through a syntactic strategy, specifically by employing the 'ane' marker. This

marker plays a crucial role in deriving constituents from both transitive and intransitive sentences, thereby facilitating the formation of nouns. The significance of this discovery lies in its ability to shed light on the complex mechanisms underlying the Balinese language, providing valuable insights into the intricate relationships between syntax and morphology.

The contribution of this study to the field of language research is multifaceted. Firstly, it highlights the importance of examining the syntactic properties of languages, particularly in the context of nominalization. By doing so, it underscores the need for a more nuanced understanding of the interplay between syntax and morphology in language formation. Furthermore, this study's findings have implications for the development of linguistic theories, as they provide evidence for the role of syntactic markers in shaping the grammatical structure of languages. Ultimately, this research has the potential to inform language teaching and learning practices, enabling educators to develop more effective pedagogical approaches that take into account the unique characteristics of the Balinese language.

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